

Neutron Stars and the EOS of Dense Matter III: From Toy Models to Nature

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Summary

Our history and knowledge of both neutron stars and the nucleus has progressed only incrementally over the past 90 years since the original work of Oppenheimer and others. We have explored the current state of the art in neutron star modelling in three installments: (1) several historic and current equations of state (EOS), (2) rotations and vibrations with a glimpse at universal love compliance, and here (3) toy models of the EOS. Pretty much all of the models of the nuclear as well as neutron star EOS are in fact TOY models. The model that represents neutron stars in nature is unknown. This is because of the paucity of precise data on both high density nuclear matter and neutron stars. Over the past two decades, the main “progress” has been *experimental* measurements from limited gravitational wave data and statistical prior methods (which are useless in the absence of more detailed data and more accurate theory). In the nuclear realm, we seem to still, after over 40 years, be unable to say unambiguously what the

nuclear compressibility and symmetry energy are to at least a few percent accuracy. Here we look at a TOY model approach which can to good precision reproduce most of the other models of the neutron star EOS. Interestingly, the Tooper EOS is a much better fit to most of the models rather than the standard polynomial fit used by Chan and others. This fact may have implications for universality and its limitations in nature with respect to REAL neutron stars.

Introduction

This work follows up on a previous study of neutron stars [1]. Over the past 40 years [2] there has been some limited progress [3] in the understanding of the equation of state (EOS) of ultra-dense matter. The compressibility remains known only to about 10% and the symmetry energy parameters are even less well known, though much discussed [3]. The seminal work was done long ago by Tolman [4] and Oppenheimer [5] and appears in most textbooks [6]. Nevertheless, a variety of models [7] continue to proliferate some with exotic features such as with cores of strange matter, quark matter, or dark matter. Some have even proposed changes to general relativity itself because of both the need to connect more fundamentally with quantum physics and due to new cosmology data. It appears from our investigations that relatively simple models [8] are able to account for current data and also a few future high precision measurements [9] of neutron star observables may be used to rule out or in softer or more exotic EOS.

Our Investigation

We have undertaken a relatively straightforward investigation using the TOV equation

- $$\frac{dp}{dr} = -G \frac{m \rho}{r^2} (1 + 4 \frac{p r^3}{m c^2}) (1 + \frac{p}{\rho c^2}) / (1 - 2 \frac{GM}{r c^2}) \quad (\text{eq 0})$$

and a few simple models which are solved analytically (where possible) or numerically when necessary [10]. Further, we have solved the slowly rotating neutron star coupled equations [11].

Also we have solved the Riccati equation [12] which allows the determination of the second Love number [13]. The TOY model approach here described draws loosely on the work of Vikaris as well as Jiang and Yagi [4].

The Vikiaris approach involves an expansion in the density (or radius) to the second (or higher) degree whereas Jiang and Yagi use an expansion in the radius of degree four. A radial expansion to degree six seems to work best and so we use that as our TOY model:

- $\rho[r] = \rho_c \{1 - \alpha (r/R)^2 + \alpha_1 (r/R)^4 + \alpha_2 (r/R)^6\}$ (equation 1)

which may be easily solved with the TOV equation approach [1]. The pressure, baryon density, mass/r^3 , $\exp[-2 \lambda]$, and $\exp[2 \nu]$ may also be expanded in the same way. Our fundamental equation is thus (equation 1). Sometimes $x=r/R$ is used and so this variable ranges from 0 to 1.

In order to illustrate the use of this relatively simple TOY model, we have extracted the parameters α and α_1 from our NUC202 and NUC274 neutron star models. α is quadratic in a parameter $xx=M/R^3/\rho_c$ and α_1 is linear with respect to α . The α s are dependent on the equation of state and the third parameter α_1 is fixed by the surface boundary condition value $\rho[R]/\rho_c$.

Considering the corresponding expansion for the pressure

- $p[r] = p_c \{1 - \pi_0 (r/R)^2 + \pi_1 (r/R)^4 + \pi_2 (r/R)^6\}$ (equation 2)

where p_c is the central pressure and the pressure parameters may be found from the α parameters or as a quadratic function of xx (for π_0) and π_1 is a linear function of π_0 (or α).

The pressure parameters π_0 , π_1 do not appear to be dependent on the EOS although the stiffness certainly does influence R , M , and p_c . To a very good approximation R is about 12 km across the beta (compactness) domain of interest [1]. Also defining $p_c = \text{sigc} \rho_c c^2$ one can use a parametrization of $\text{sigc}[\text{bet}]$ to determine the central pressure. See Figures 1 and 2 in this regard.

The Vikiaris model referred to in the figures is similar to equations (1) and (2) but with parameters α_{VIK} , $\alpha_{1\text{VIK}}$, and $\alpha_{2\text{VIK}}$ which are defined not by fits to another model but by equations involving ρ_c , p_c , $dp/d\rho_c$, $\gamma_{\text{mac}} = \rho_c/p_c (dp/d\rho_c)_c$, etc. For example

- $\alpha_{\text{VIK}} = \frac{2}{3} \text{Pi} (G/c^2) (R^2) (p_c + \rho_c c^2) (\rho_c + 3 p_c/c^2)/(dp/d\rho_c \rho_c)$ (eq 3)

and

- $\pi_{\text{VIK}} = \rho_c/p_{\text{csc}} \alpha_{\text{VIK}} dp/d\rho_c$. (equation 4)

Similar but more complicated equations exist for $\alpha_{1\text{VIK}}$ and $\pi_{1\text{VIK}}$. The third set of parameters may be then derived from the requirement that $\rho[r]=0$ (or a surface value) and $p[R]=0$.

Figures 3 and 4 show how the simple Vikiaris model relates to our TOY model. The case shown is for $\beta=0.107$ and $\rho_c=5.28 \cdot 10^{14}$ g/cc. The TOY model density is input into the TOV equation for a numerical solution. The analytic Vikiaris model is seen to agree pretty well in this case.

Integrating our TOY model fundamental equation (1) as input to the TOV equation (0) also gives the mass M which must also be related to the radius R via the standard expression $\beta = G M/(R c^2)$. Since $\bar{\rho} = M/R^3/\rho_c$ this approach may be used iteratively to determine the best parameters to use in (1).

Figures 5 and 6 show the same parameters for the density and pressure equations plotted versus compactness β .

Vibrations

For calculating frequencies of vibration, we consider two approaches [1], that due to Bardeen [7] and Chandrasekhar (radial) which defines quantities P, Q, W in terms of the density and pressure profile of the star and related quantities $PLMI, QLMI, WLMI$ due to Lindblom, Mendell, Ipson [4, 7] and others (non-radial). Mostly we shall focus on the LMI frequencies since they are of interest in the tidal deformation process which leads to the gravitational waves that have now been observed.

Results

Our main results are given in Figures 7 through 9. Figure 7 shows the frequency ratio as a function of the neutron star z shift. The agreement with the more sophisticated NUC202 and NUC274 models is very good. The nuclear EOS mainly appears to make a difference around a z shift of $z=0.15$. Figure 8 shows the moment of inertia (scaled) vs. the tidal deformability. Again, the agreement with the other models and limited data [9] is very good. The Chan universal love expansion is a good approximation over this range of tidal deformability. A tidal deformability of about 300 is thought to occur experimentally; this corresponds to a 11.5 love number in the Chan formula.

Recall that this Chan expansion is given by

- $\text{ChanIlove}[x] =$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2}{5} (2x)^{2/5} \left(1 + \frac{22}{7} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right)^{1/5} + \frac{8726}{2205} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right)^{2/5} + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{79840}{33957} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right)^{3/5} + \frac{10621396}{21068775} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right)^{4/5} - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{495373192}{4866887025} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right) - \frac{29520935754944}{286683980207625} \left(\frac{1}{2x} \right)^{6/5} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where x is the tidal deformability. Aside from this big integer expansion, numerical fits for I_{love} , Q_{love} , and tidal λ relationships are available from Chan and others. On a more precise and observable linear scale some violations are expected in particular with models such as the Tooper variety. Some of the deviations go away with corrections due to surface density and/or pressure (when appropriate). Just as there is a moment of inertia I Love number

- $\text{momlove} = I/M^3 (c^2/G)^2$

there is also a quadrupole moment Q Love number

- $\text{quadLove} = Q (c^2/G)^4 / \text{momlove}^2 / M^5 c^2 / \text{bigom}^2$

where M is the star mass and bigom is the rotational frequency. See Figures 9.

Parameter trends

Some of the trends of the first and second order parameters are shown in our final figures 10 and 11. Much of the data lies within three standard deviations of the Tolman α value of 1.

Figure 10 and 11 show some of the many parameters for quantities which permit an even power expansion (2,4,6 power e.g.) like density, pressure, $dp/d\rho$, $\text{mass}/(4/3 \pi r^3)$, $\exp[-2 \lambda]$, $\exp[2 \nu]$, and $BE = d1m/m = a \text{bet} b \text{bet}^2 c \text{bet}^3$ with a about .70 shown. The drawn guidelines are

the Tolman alpha value of 1, the scaled (1) Tolman pizero value of 2.5 (divided by 2.5), and the two black lines with upper 3 sigma and lower 3 sigma above the Tolman unitary value. Obviously there is some beta dependence in the models, as in nature. At the high end, for example lam0 the first term (coefficient of $(r/R)^2$) in the $\exp[-2 \text{ lam}]$ expansion tends to 5 bet which is the exact Tolman 7 value. At the low beta end, nuzero in the $\exp[2 \text{ nu}]$ expansion tends to 2 bet whereas at the high end it goes to bet. Absolute values of the parameters are shown for ease of plotting. In our calculations we of course use exact (not approximate or expanded) values of the Schwarzschild Einstein variables lam and nu.

Other models

The variety of models that may be studied both directly and in this TOY model expansion approach is illustrated in Figure 12, which shows the pressure evolution in the various models typically for $\text{bet}=.107$ and $\text{rhoME}=5.28 \cdot 10^{14}$ g/cc central density. The IBEN model [18], though unrealistic due to the doubly large size (22 km), can also be a good reference due to its simplicity. The Lake/Hernandez/Heintzmann [17] family of models represent a large easily accessible class, some of which are similar to Tolman 4. See Figure 3b for the associated density profiles.

Of interest in all the models is the parameter gammac which is the generalization of the logarithmic derivative $\text{gamma}=\text{d Ln}[p]/\text{d Ln} [\text{rho}]$ used most directly in the Tooper ($p=k \text{ rho}^{\text{gamma}}$) model. This is shown in Figure 13.

Finally the fundamental derivative, which was first introduced in a military paper by Bethe some years ago [18], may be calculated from $dp/d\rho$ and various derivatives. Typically, one refers to a classical and a relativistic fundamental derivative. For an ideal gas, the classical value is $G_c = (\gamma + 1)/2$ where γ is typically $5/3$ or $7/5$. The relativistic version is $G_r = G_c - 3/2 \cdot cr^2/c^2$ where cr^2 is just $dp/d\rho$. One may also define a compressibility (K) related fundamental derivative by $G_{comp} = 1/2(1 + \rho_{ob}/K \cdot dK/d\rho_{ob})$ where ρ_{ob} is the baryon density. For the Tooper model, $dp/d\rho = \gamma(p/\rho)$. The relativistic version of the fundamental derivative is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 15 is an alternate to Figure 7: frequency vs. z shift as a ratio to a base frequency. Note that the Hern/Hein/Lake $N=3$ model gives relatively large frequencies such as the Tolman 4 and Tolman 4 Lake variety models. The IBEN model (not shown) produces somewhat smaller frequencies than all the other models.

Figures 16 display how many of the expansions compare to the GTM model where

- $\rho = \rho_{oc} (1 - \delta x^2)$

which can be useful because of its simplicity and that the range from $\delta=0$ to $\delta=1$ spans the model universe from Maximum Uniform to Tolman 7. There are similarities in results to the Tooper model

- $p/\rho c = (\rho/\rho_{oc})^\gamma$

where $\gamma = 2$ to $\gamma = \text{large}$ (e.g. ten or greater) also spans the universe of models.

Interestingly, the Tooper EOS is a much better fit to most of the models rather than the standard

polynomial fit used by Chan and others. This fact may have implications for universality and its limitations in nature with respect to REAL neutron stars.

Select tabular results

Select tabular results are shown in the below table. Note that these are NOT for the largest mass neutron star for each model. For maximum mass neutron star values, see Figure 9 of the second paper [1] in this series. A typical value of $\rho_{MEc}=5.28 \cdot 10^{14}$ g/cc is used; for most of the models this produces (or one can choose) $\beta=.107$.

Table 1. Select results for the main two EOS and reference models. ρ_{bC} is in units of 10^{15} g/cc; r is in km; m is in solar masses. Pressure is in cgs units of 10^{35} erg/cc. The frequencies are in units of Hz. Γ_{mac} and G_{drel} are dimensionless.

Table 1. Select results.

EOS	ρ_{bC}	r	m	pc	l_{ove}	α_0	ν_{Bar}	ν_{LMI}	Γ_{mac}	G_{drel}
NUC274	0.499	12.2	1.0	0.379	26	0.800	2475	2275	2.77	1.58
NUC202	0.500	12.2	0.89	0.320	32	0.978	2189	2212	2.47	1.51
Tolman 7	0.502	12.7	0.93	0.334	30	1	2257	1844	2.63	1.62
Tooper	0.511	11.0	0.81	0.326	30	0.735	3075	1950	3.21	1.86
Nariai	0.505	13.2	0.96	0.341	30	0.904	2668	1850	3.19	2.08
Buchdahl	0.502	12.6	0.92	0.349	30	0.713	2440	1824	3.39	2.60
Tolman 4	0.522	9.0	0.65	0.302	38	0.416	7036	7646	3.32	0.48
Hein3	0.525	8.5	0.62	0.314	39	0.189	10.3 k	10.6 k	6.43	0.41
GTM	0.514	9.7	0.75	0.332	33	0.430				

Conclusions

The effect of most changes to the EOS - such as moderately changing the stiffness or limiting the sound speed - is within the ten percent uncertainty of the data. A fairly simple TOY model has here been presented which also relates to the Vikiaris model. This TOY model may be used to represent or approximate most other EOS models (my NUC202, NUC274, Tolman, Buchdahl, Tooper, Nariai, etc.) to fairly good precision since the parameters are determined by a fit to the known density distribution for each model. Previously, we had investigated the maximal neutron star mass for both realistic and other EOS [1]. We find that the mass is about 2 solar masses with radii of 12 km in accord with the experimental data. The effect of limiting the speed of sound squared in neutron matter to $.5 c^2$ is to reduce the mass (2.2 to 1.9 solar masses for $K=274$ or 1.9 to 1.8 for $K=202$) or change the radius of the neutron star by less than ten percent [1].

Interestingly, the Tooper EOS is a much better fit to most of the models rather than the standard polynomial fit used by Chan and others. This fact may have implications for universality and its limitations in nature with respect to REAL neutron stars.

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Figures

Figure 1: density parameter alpha versus alternate compactness parameter

- $\alpha = M / (\rho c R^3) = c^2 / G \beta / (\rho c R^2)$.

Figure 2: pressure parameter p_{zero} versus alternate compactness parameter

Figure 3a: density profile for a $\beta=0.107$ neutron star with a realistic NUC202 EOS versus the Vikiaris analytic model.

Figure 3b: density profile for $\beta=0.107$ neutron stars in various models.

Figure 4a: pressure profile for a $\beta=0.107$ neutron star with a realistic NUC202 EOS versus the Vikiaris analytic model. The two are nearly identical!

Figure 4b: pressure profile for $\beta=0.107$ neutron stars in various models.

Figure 5: density parameter alpha versus compactness parameter $\beta = GM/Rc^2$

Figure 6: pressure parameter p_{zero} versus compactness parameter $\beta = GM/Rc^2$

Figure 7: frequency vs. z shift as a ratio to a base frequency given by

- $\nu_{\text{base}} = \sqrt{GM/R^3} / (2\pi)$

Figure 8a: scaled moment of inertia (the so called love number) versus the tidal deformability. On the log scale the agreement with the Chan universal formula is pretty good. A tidal deformability of about 300 is thought to occur experimentally; this corresponds to a 11.5 love number in the Chan formula. The plot shown is BEFORE various corrections due to surface density and other items which tend to shift the curves toward the Chan expansion line.

Figure 8b: scaled moment of inertia versus the beta compactness parameter. Some results from Lattimer are also shown for reference.

Figure 9a: Love number versus the Chan value as a ratio on a linear scale shows apparent universality violations in particular for models like the Tooper variety (also Tolman 4 normal and Lake variant shown) where there is a non-vanishing density at the surface (such as with most objects like a rock or the Earth). The plot shown is BEFORE various corrections due to surface density and other items which tend to shift the curves toward the Chan expansion line.

Figure 9b: Love numbers corrected. The agreement with universality is very good.

Figure 10: some of the many parameters for quantities which permit an even power expansion (2,4,6 power e.g.) like density, pressure, $dp/d\rho$, $mass/(4/3 \pi r^3)$, and $BE = d1m/m = a \text{ bet} + b \text{ bet}^2 + c \text{ bet}^3$ with a about .70 shown.

Figure 11: some of the many parameters for quantities which permit an even power expansion (2,4,6 power e.g.) like density, pressure, $dp/d\rho$, $mass/(4/3 \pi r^3)$, $\exp[-2 \text{ lam}]$, $\exp[2 \text{ nu}]$, and $BE = d1m/m = a \text{ bet } b \text{ bet}^2 \text{ c bet}^3$ with a about .70 shown. The drawn guidelines are the Tolman alpha value of 1, the scaled (1) Tolman pizero value of 2.5 (divided by 2.5), and the two black lines with upper 3 sigma and lower 3 sigma above the Tolman unitary value. Obviously there is some beta dependence in the models, as in nature. At the high end, for example lam0 the first term (coefficient of $(r/R)^2$) in $\exp[-2 \text{ lam}]$ expansion tends to 5 bet which is the exact Tolman 7 value. At the low beta end, nuzero in the $\exp[2 \text{ nu}]$ expansion tends to 2 bet whereas at the high end it goes to bet. Absolute values of the parameters are shown for ease of plotting.

Figure 12. Pressure in the various models typically for $\beta=0.107$ and $\rho_{MEC}=5.28 \times 10^{14}$ g/cc.

Figure 13. Gammac in the various models.

Figure 14. The relativistic fundamental derivative.

Figure 15. Alternate to Figure 7: frequency vs. z shift as a ratio to a base frequency. Note that the Hern/Hein/Lake N=3 model gives relatively large frequencies such as the Tolman 4 and Tolman 4 Lake variety models. The IBEN model (not shown) produces somewhat smaller frequencies than all the other models.

Figures 16a display how many of the expansions compare to the GTM models. Density dependence.

Figures 16b display how many of the expansions compare to the GTM models. Pressure dependence.

Figures 16c display how many of the expansions compare to the GTM models. Scaled density and pressure dependence.

Figures 16d display how many of the expansions compare to the GTM models. Scaled density and pressure dependence.

